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Executive summary

This deliverable reports on the results of the conducted evaluation activities. THEIA^{XR} pursued a human-centred and prototype-based testing of the XR demonstrators to determine effectivity of the developed technologies and the levels to which the commensurable project goals have been achieved.

Continuous evaluation activities throughout the project were also essential within the development in identifying optimization potentials and design recommendations. Our defined project goals encompass safety, privacy, work performance and quality of work factors. We understand that implementing XR technologies alone is not enough to solve the challenges that come with digitalizing machine operation. Instead, XR interaction must be designed precisely to meet the requirements and expectations. It must provide clear benefits (e.g., operation performance) that must outweigh potential cost (e.g., adaptation, impaired intuitiveness, information overload). Many technical and human factors impact this trade-off and the applicability and performance of the outcomes.

This final version presents the results of our conducted baseline and demonstrator evaluation using functional lab and machine-based prototypes. This deliverable is structured as follows: Section 1 gives a brief overview about the evaluated KPIs, section 2 describes the methodological framework applied in the evaluation activities, the conducted evaluation procedures, used prototypes and data assessment and analysis procedures, section 3 reports the result of the evaluation and section 4 concludes with discussing the results.

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1 Introduction

THEIA^{XR} researched novel ways to connect experienced machine operators with advanced digital technologies and services through XR technologies embedded in real machine operation scenarios. It is the aim of this project to demonstrate how such technologies can improve machine operation across several criteria through appropriate information presentation, visualization form and interactivity, recognizing the operators' mental capabilities, expectations and attitudes towards technology. XR must provide clear benefits (e.g., operation performance) that must outweigh potential cost (e.g., adaptation, impaired intuitiveness, information overload). THEIA^{XR} applied an iterative development process that involves the consideration and evaluation of human factors and work performance criteria regarding a defined set of KPIs.

Number & Use Case	Key Performance Indicator	
Task performance-based criteria		
KPI 1.1a	UC1, UC2, UC3	Improvement of safety for humans, equipment and cargo. We plan to identify and eliminate at least three common situations of human error or danger through design concepts.
KPI 1.1b	UC2	Perceived presence, awareness and responsibility will be measured in the status quo, these values need to be significantly surpassed by the prototypes.
KPI 1.2	UC1, UC2, UC3	Reassurance of intuitiveness and usability . Ease of use of the current machine operation modalities will be measured by questionnaires and user tests. These values must be matched in our XR prototypes to ensure that the 'virtual cabin' and its additional information and interaction modalities will not be detrimental to the ease of use.
KPI 2.1	UC1, UC2, UC3	Utility of augmenting information in work task completion above conventional HMI functionality, evaluated through performance measures such as time on task, situational awareness and work quality .
KPI 2.2	Gen.	Improved usability of XR interface design, evaluated through usability measures (e.g., SUS, and UEQ - aim: at least reach a "good" evaluation on the pragmatic scales according to the benchmarking by [12]).
KPI 2.3	Gen.	Better predictability of system behaviour, evaluated through observation and user questionnaire.
KPI 2.4	Gen.	Improved comprehensibility of system behaviour evaluated through observation and user questionnaire.
KPI 4.1	Gen.	Identify privacy principles to be fulfilled in the design solution, leading to measurable privacy and UX outcomes, measured for instance with UEQ, meCUE or similar. The objective will be to iteratively improve the solutions, leading to positive outcomes for both UX and privacy perceptions . Where available, we will use benchmarks from these tools to evaluate our comparative UX and privacy outcomes.

KPI 4.2	Gen.	Improvement of quality of work as a result of psychological need fulfilment and positive experiences at work. Measurement of the need fulfilment, and specifically self-efficacy and meaningfulness of work, in the current work environment and in prototype/demonstrator. We aim for a perceived increase of at least one point on average in the respective scales for at least two psychological needs.
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Table 1: List of use-case related (UCX) and general (Gen.) KPIs. Technology and dissemination related KPIs are not considered in this deliverable

For evaluating our XR technologies we recognize (1) task performance, (2) perceived qualities, and (3) human factor-based criteria. In industrial use cases, **task performance** is determined through a set of key criteria (e.g., productivity, efficiency, and safety). They refer to different states and situations and may interact with each other, creating conflicts of objectives (e.g., productivity vs. safety). Despite aiming to improve these parameters, user interfaces are also regularly evaluated against interaction qualities. **Perceived quality** metrics such as usability and user experience (UUX), intuitiveness and perceived ease of use reflect to what extent the technologies and user interfaces appearance, functionality, and performance meet the operator’s requirements in work tasks. Interaction performance of operators with distinct user interfaces also relate to a set of prominent **human factors** in interaction and user interface research. Among them are situational awareness, acceptance or workload. Quality of work as a hedonistic quality and can be measured through standardized questionnaires to assess the fulfilment of basic needs. Another dimension of criteria is situation related. Different situations require evaluation of different information or the proficient use of different system functions to be effectively and efficiently solved. Thus, reliable measurement of HMI qualities must be performed in the context of a task or situation. Table 2 summarizes the evaluation criteria we applied based on the projects KPIs.

Eval. criteria	KPIs	Description
Task performance-based criteria		
Work Performance	2.1	Work performance refers to the efficiency, effectiveness, and reliability of a machine or automated system in carrying out its intended tasks or functions. It involves assessing various metrics such as speed, accuracy, throughput, uptime, downtime, and energy consumption. It encompasses various aspects, including accuracy, completeness, effectiveness, efficiency, reliability, and consistency. Quality of work is often evaluated based on how well it meets predefined criteria, standards, or expectations, as well as its overall impact on achieving organizational goals or fulfilling customer needs. Achieving high-quality work involves attention to detail, adherence to standards and best practices, continuous improvement efforts, and a commitment to delivering value to stakeholders [1].
Safety	1.1	Safety is often considered as the most important operational criteria and refers to design and functional features that help to prevent accidents, machine abuse and operational errors. The higher the operational safety of a system is, the lower the probabilities of these occurring [2][3].
Perceived qualities		
Usability	1.2	Usability is the extent to which a product can be used by specified users to achieve specified goals with effectiveness, efficiency and satisfaction in a specified context of use [4]. Usability refers to the ease with which people can use a product or system to achieve their goals effectively, efficiently, and satisfactorily [3]. It involves assessing how user-friendly

		and intuitive a product or system is, considering factors such as learnability (how easy it is for users to understand and use the product), efficiency (how quickly users can perform tasks), memorability (how easily users can remember how to use the product over time), error prevention and recovery (how well the product helps users avoid and correct mistakes), and satisfaction (how pleasant and satisfying the user experience is). Usability is essential in design to enhance user experience, increase user adoption, and ultimately improve the success and acceptance of a product or system [5].
Intuitiveness	2.2	Intuitiveness refers to the fit between an HMI's design and appearance and the users' expectations and mental models. Poor intuitiveness can significantly impair operation performance, workload and satisfaction, that will very likely result in poor usability and performance ratings. Intuitiveness is sometimes associated to be a part of usability [6].
Predictability	2.3	Predictability refers to how well users can anticipate the system's responses to their actions based on prior interactions and visible cues. A predictable interface behaves consistently, follows clear rules, and provides understandable feedback, allowing users to form accurate mental models, reduce cognitive load, and act with confidence, especially in time-critical or safety-relevant situations [7].
Comprehensibility	2.4	Comprehensibility refers to how easily users can understand what the system is doing, what information is presented, and how to interact with it. A comprehensible interface uses clear representations, meaningful labels, and transparent logic, enabling users to interpret system states and functions correctly without unnecessary effort or prior training [6].
Human factors-based criteria		
Situation Awareness	2.1	Situation awareness (SA) refers to the understanding and perception of the environment and the dynamic elements within it, including events, objects, people, and their interactions [9]. It involves being aware of relevant information, predicting future developments, and making effective decisions based on this understanding. Situation awareness is crucial in various contexts, such as aviation, military operations, healthcare, and emergency response, where individuals need to monitor and comprehend complex situations rapidly and accurately to respond appropriately. Effective situation awareness relies on factors such as perception, comprehension, projection, and decision-making, as well as the ability to filter and prioritize relevant information amidst distractions or uncertainties [10].
Quality of Work	4.2	Quality of work describes a hedonistic quality in work (Quality in work life), focusing more on individual joy and need fulfilment through facilitating work conditions [8].
Trust/Privacy concerns	4.1	Privacy concerns refer to how well the interface makes data collection, use, and sharing visible, understandable, and controllable for users. A privacy-respecting interface clearly communicates what data is involved, why it is needed, and provides intuitive controls for consent and data management, thereby supporting user trust and informed decision-making. It is necessary to mention that privacy-by-design is just a component of value-sensitive design, therefore perception of privacy should be analysed along with perception of other ethical values in work (e.g., autonomy or sense of belonging) [11].

Table 2: List of evaluation criteria based on defined KPIs

Achieving good ratings regarding these criteria not only serves the technologies worthiness but also contributes to the likelihood of the technologies being accepted by machine operators. Technology acceptance refers to the willingness and readiness of individuals or groups to adopt and use a new technology. It involves understanding the factors that influence users' perceptions and attitudes toward technology adoption, including perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and other social and organizational factors. The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and its variations provide frameworks for studying and predicting users' intentions to adopt technology based on these factors. Successful technology acceptance occurs when users perceive the technology as beneficial, easy to use, and compatible with their needs, leading to widespread adoption and utilization of the technology within an organization or society [12].

2 Method

Whereas different stages of prototypes were used throughout the project to explore and evaluate XR technologies, this deliverable reports on the final end-user evaluation of THEIA^{XR} technologies.

2.1 Overall Method

Most of the XR features aim for presenting information closer in the field of view of operators that focus on the environment of the machine. Reducing complexity and actively guiding attention through feedback signals and dynamic and adjustable visual complexity are other approaches that aim to support operators in gaining situational awareness. However, such novel information presentation modalities may also come with negative effects, e.g., higher workload through the increase of presented information and the use of unfamiliar cues, number of simultaneous signals and signal complexity, that can lead to distraction, high workload and confusion with impacts on work performance. A careful design is essential to utilize the potential of XR technology while to limiting these impairments. THEIA^{XR} deployed a prototype-based evaluation strategy involving end users and other stakeholders to keep track of these issues from technical, psychological, social and cognitive perspectives.

For the final evaluation of our XR technologies, a series of experiments were designed to collect (1) baseline data and (2) XR technology ratings regarding the listed criteria above. Both types of experiments were conducted in realistic task scenarios or real work environments, involved end users and supplementary questionnaires to collect qualitative and quantitative data. XR technology ratings were assessed using functional high-fidelity demonstrators that showcased realistic behaviour and functionality of our developed XR features in all three use cases.

2.2 Prototypes

Several approaches on how to utilize XR interaction for machine operation have been developed. While many of them are applicable in more than one use case, interaction concepts for each use case comprises distinct configurations and combinations that meet the specific requirements. The HMI concepts combine several sub-systems of interactive functions based on different information origins or work procedures. Even though these will work simultaneously, our scientific evaluation approach focuses on the performance evaluation of these sub systems. This section provides a short summary of the involved sub-systems as listed in Table 3.

XR Technology	Test Use Cases	Description
Object Recognition with Light Feedback	UC1, UC3	This XR-technology consists of an object detection system, that analyses video footage of an array of cameras mounted on the machine. It identifies if a person is in the covered area around the machine and provides real-time information about its position through a spatial mapping on an LED-strip permanently mounted on the operation environment.
Virtual Pit geometry/tool guidance with Matrix Display and Light Feedback	UC3	This XR-technology consists of a virtual model of the machine based on real time data of implemented sensors that measure positions of machine components and the machine as a whole relative to the environments. It uses reference 3D models to calculate spatial deviations between tool or machine positions that are then displayed as visual indicators on a LED matrix display or Light-Strip.
Calibrated environment projection	UC1	This XR-technology consists of a laser projection in the environment that is spatially calibrated through video reference data to either align with geometric features in the environment or to show prospectively correct visuals from the operator's point of view.
LiDAR augmented 3D Data on GUI	UC3	This XR-technology uses spatial and visual data from a LiDAR sensor attached to the machine, recording the environment around the machine that is affected by the machine's tools. This data is then spatially overlaid with a reference 3D model displayed on a terminal at the operation environment.
Remote Operation Terminal with augmented camera streams	UC2	This XR technology consists of a monitoring and control station that uses virtually augmented multi-camera footage. Augmentations include spatially aligned visuals and graphic overlays on the environment.
Haptic Feedback Joystick	UC1, UC2	This XR-technology consists of a joystick with active haptic and force feedback to reproduce or augment real-life feedback in machine operation.
Thermal camera with object recognition	UC1	This XR-technology consists of an array of thermal cameras with advanced image quality in low illumination conditions. Video streams from several cameras are stitched for a live 360° video stream.

Table 3: List of XR technologies and their involvement in use case specific XR environments

Figure 1 gives some impressions about the realized prototypes used for evaluation activities in use cases 1 – snow grooming (a, b, and c), use cases 2 – logistics (d, g, and h) and use case 3 – construction (e, and f). Picture (a) shows the equipped snow groomer cabin, (b) shows the task simulation and (c) shows a moment during data assessment with a snow groomer operator. Picture (d) shows the reachstacker equipped with the camera arrays and the remote-control system, (g) shows one of the visual overlays that augment the

camera streams at the desk-based remote operation environment visible in picture (h). Picture (e) shows the equipped excavator and (f) the mobile demonstrator with task simulation in virtual reality.

Figure 1: THEIA^{XR} prototypes used for user-centred technology evaluation

The operation of a **snow groomer** (UC1) is becoming more difficult, as digitalization of the work environment (e.g., use of 3D data for slope planning) leads to more information that is available and the operator must take care of. Further, work on ski slopes, which often occurs at night, creates difficult work conditions (e.g., skiers around the vehicle, environment conditions, etc.) challenging the operator's situational awareness. The operation environment temperature ranges from -35°C up to 20°C , with sun, rain, snow fall, ice rain, fog, wind and darkness that can further impair this factor. Operators must constantly keep their hands on the controls and thus cannot directly interact with the available data on display-based interfaces. Additionally, much of the environment around the vehicle is not visible to the operator, or at least not in an easy to perceive manner. The XR features we applied in this use case comprise different augmenting information presentations that give the operator additional information about the presence and position of obstacles, slope profile, tool setup, navigation and area restrictions through augmented and spatially aligned visual guidance and haptic feedback. Table 4 provides a list of realized lab and machine-based prototypes for this use case.

Our XR setup for use case 2 (UC2) comprises a remote-control setup for **reachstackers**, where operators work with multiple visually augmented video screens and haptic feedback joysticks. From the footage, they observe how the container approaches the landing point in a truck, another container or cassette and how it settles on its place. Depth is difficult to estimate through video. Supporting the operator to perceive spatial information from the real environment and to stay aware of items not visible in the cameras is supported by visual aids, presented as spatially aligned overlays in the camera streams. Since the visibility and feeling of presence (the sounds, vibrations and movements of the machine) are not on the same level in remote operation than driving a machine from the cabin, it is very important that the operators feel that they are

controlling the machine in a safe and predictable manner, and they have enough information about the surroundings. The XR systems implemented in this use case comprises different augmenting information presentations that give the operator additional information about the presence and position of obstacles, tool position, tool setup, navigation and area restrictions through visual and haptic forms of augmenting feedback. Table 4 provides a list of realized lab and machine-based prototypes for this use case.

Excavator (UC3) operators are confronted with an increasing demand for infrastructure and residential building while it's facing a significant lack in skilled labour and technological development, i.e., digitalization and automation. Higher task load and changing machine functionalities are consequences. Assistance systems, automated machines and construction robotics, model-based workflows and ubiquitous connectivity are the key factors to leverage the productivity in the construction sector, especially in earth-moving machinery. Hence, HMIs are getting complex and thus counterintuitive. Besides operating the machine, operators are facing tasks like handling and manipulating digital models, controlling collaborating machine fleets as well as surveying and documenting the work results. Heterogeneous environmental influences, significant noise and vibration levels and a very busy surrounding challenge the operator's situational awareness. The XR systems implemented in this use case comprises different augmenting information presentations that give the operator additional information about the presence and position of obstacles, tool position, tool setup, navigation and area restrictions through augmenting direct visual and ambient light feedback. Table 4 provides a list of realized lab and machine-based prototypes for this use case.

The following use case-based prototypes reached high-fidelity levels and were used for XR technology evaluation:

Prototype	Description	Used in final evaluation activities (see Table 6)
Use Case 1 – Snow grooming		
Equipped machine (PRIN)	Snow groomer equipped with laser and light projectors and panoramic thermal camera.	None, demonstration only
Demo Cabin + Simulation (PRIN)	Vehicle cabin, equipped with light feedback system and a haptic feedback joystick, combined with screen-based simulation of a ski slope.	5
Lab Cabin with simulation (TUD)	Mock-up machine cabin, equipped with light feedback system, ground projection system and control elements to adapt means of the XR features, combined with screen-based simulation of a ski slope.	None, design improvement studies only
Use Case 2 – Logistics		
Equipped machine (KAL)	Reachstacker equipped with camera system to live stream into an off-site remote operation environment.	8
Lab Work Environment Simulation (VTT)	Remote operation environment, equipped with a haptic feedback joystick, combined with screen-based simulation of a container terminal.	6,7
Use Case 3 – Construction		
Equipped machine (TUD)	Excavator equipped with a light feedback system, matrix display, LiDAR sensor and camera array	None, demonstration and functional testing only
Mobile Demo + Simulation (TUD)	Compact simulator equipped with two joysticks, a monitor, a light feedback system and a matrix display, combined with screen-based simulation of a construction pit.	9

Desk Demo + Simulation (TUD)	Monitor-based simulator equipped with two joysticks, combined with screen-based simulation of a construction pit with implemented light feedback and matrix display.	10
Lab Cabin with simulation (TUD)	Mock-up machine cabin, equipped with two joysticks, a monitor, a light feedback system, ground projection and a matrix display, combined with screen-based simulation of a construction pit.	None, design improvement studies only
Lab simulation (HdM)	Creanex simulation running on 98" monitor for life-size representation of virtual cabin, controlled via two Thrustmaster T16000M joysticks calibrated to match real excavator controls.	None, demonstration only

Table 4: List of realised high fidelity XR technology prototypes throughout all three use cases and their involvement in evaluation activities

2.3 Measures

We aimed to use standardized questionnaires for quantitative data coupled with self-designed questions to assess associated qualitative data. We built a modular evaluation tool with the web-based scientific data assessment tool SoSciSurvey [13] that was used for all data collection activities, as it could be easily customized for different evaluation scopes using different pre-defined presets. In its full length, the questionnaire included a briefing, a setup page (defining use case, evaluation (baseline or demo), used prototype and tasks), demographic data (e.g., age, gender, occupation, affinity for technology interaction, privacy concerns), test tasks (with work performance and situation awareness rating scales), perceived qualities (e.g., usability, usefulness, user experience, immersiveness (of virtual demonstrators)), and needs. Table 5 lists all taken measures, references and their association to the criteria listed above.

Eval. criteria	KPIs	Measure	Baseline	Ref.
Demographic data				
General		Age, gender, nationality, occupation, years of experience in machine operation, expertise in machine control		
Attitudes		Affinity for Technology Interaction (ATI)		[14]
Privacy and Ethics Concerns	4.1	Internet users' information privacy concerns (IUIPC)		[15]
	4.1	Online Privacy Concerns Scale		[16]
	4.1	Perception of Ethical Qualities of Prototype Scale (see deliverable D3.8)		
	4.1	General Acceptance of Technology (Ethical Dimension) (see deliverable D3.8)		
Task completion-related measures				
Work Performance	2.1	Self-designed rating scales for safety and efficiency as measures for quality of work (QoW)		
Safety	1.1	Number of crashes, noticed obstacles	x	
Situation Awareness	1.1, 2.1	Situation Awareness Rating Technique (SART)	x	[17]
Qualitative rating		General likes and dislikes, general and specific differences to conventional operation		
Perceived Qualities				
Intuitiveness	2.2	Questionnaire for Measuring the Subjective Consequences of Intuitive Use (QUESI)	x	[18]
Usability	1.2	Perceived ease of use	x	[18]

	1.2	Perceived usefulness		[19]
	1.2	System Usability Scale (SUS)		[20]
Predictability	2.3	Self-designed rating scale	x	
Comprehensibility	2.4	Self-designed rating scale	x	
User Experience	4.1	UEQ+ (Attractiveness, Trust, Trustworthiness of content)		[21]
Privacy Concerns	4.1	Measuring mobile users' concerns for information privacy questionnaire (MUIPC)		[22]
Sense of Responsibility (SoR)	1.1	Self-designed responsibility statements	x	
Positive User Experience				
Psychological needs	4.2	Sheldon Needs Questionnaire	x	[23]
Meaningful work	4.2	ME-Work Questionnaire	x	[24]
Prototyped test environment (for virtual task simulations)				
Sense of presence	1.1	Igroup Presence Questionnaire (IPQ)		[25]

Table 5: List of conducted measures and their association to the XR technology-related KPIs

2.4 Conducted Experiments and Procedures

Table 6 lists the conducted experimental activities that took place at different locations covering baseline and demonstrator evaluation data assessment.

Activity and Use Case			Measure	Participants	Date
Baselines					
1	Experience-based	UC1	All, except SoR, IPQ	Snow groomer operators	07. – 09.05.25
2	Simulation-based	UC1	All, except IPQ	Snow groomer operators	29. – 30.10.25
3	Experience-based	UC3	All, except SoR, IPQ	Excavator operators	29. – 30.10.25
4	Experience-based	UC3	All, except IPQ	Excavator operators	27.11.25
Prototype evaluations					
5	Cabin simulation evaluation	UC1	All	Snow groomer operators	03. – 17.10.25
6	Lab simulator evaluation	UC2	All	Reachstacker operators	15. – 19.12.25
7	Lab-based evaluation	UC2	SUS (Usability)	Reachstacker operators	27.2.2024
8	Equipped machine evaluation	UC2	Work performance	Reachstacker operators	22.11. – 2.12.25
9	Lab simulator evaluation	UC3	All	Excavator operators	1. – 12.12.25
10	Mobile simulator evaluation	UC3	All	Excavator operators	10. – 11.12.25

Table 6: List of conducted evaluation activities and assessed measures

The **baseline evaluations** used observations, questionnaires and interviews with different stakeholders at different venues (see Table 6). These served to collect data on conventional work procedures, information requirements and needs of machine operators across all three use cases. For use case 1, baselines were collected from snow groomer operators, both based on operator experience and with a baseline simulation without any assistance technologies enabled. In use case 3, baselines were collected mainly from operators of a construction vehicle training centre based on experience. For use case 2, baselines were assessed with comparative ratings, that asked participant to state whether they think they performed better than with conventional machine operation environments. Assessing baseline ratings from real machine use was not possible in use case 2, as we were not able to find reachstacker operators that wanted to participate. In general, openness for evaluation activities and motivation to participate highly differed between use cases. However, all activities, covering all use cases contributed to an overall understanding of how our XR technologies can impact work procedures in off-highway domains.

The **prototype evaluations** used an online questionnaire on tablet in combination with in-presence test trials using the different XR technology prototypes across all use cases. End users were invited to the labs, the test sites, or we visited training centres for data collection. We started with a brief introduction to the project and the purpose of the evaluation. After setting up the questionnaire by selecting the use case and the evaluation type (baseline or demonstrator evaluation), experiment supervisors also selected the used prototype and were able to make remarks if the experiment setup had any deviation to the planned design. The tablet with the questionnaire was then handed to the participant. As a first step, participants were provided a standardized consent form that they could accept or decline. They were then asked to answer questions regarding their demographic and work background, their attitudes towards technology interaction and privacy concerns. This was followed by an introduction of the task-based test phase that involved three different tasks and the assessment of work performance, general likes and dislikes and perceived situational awareness during task completion after each task. For each task, the participants were given a clear task instruction where they had to perform certain machine operation procedures to fulfil the tasks. Participants were able to familiarize themselves with the interactive prototypes/machine simulations, and the first task started when they signalled that they feel ready. After five minutes of working, the experiment supervisor stopped the participants and asked them to answer the follow-up questions. This was repeated until all three tasks and the associated follow-up questionnaires were completed. Participants were then asked to complete the post-task questionnaire that consisted of a set of standardized questionnaires about how they perceived certain aspects of the XR technologies presented. The questionnaire ended with some open questions, that were recorded, and the opportunity to give some statements and opinions. Data were collected by the online questionnaire tool, hosted on a local Server at Technische Universität Dresden. No personal data was stored. Answers were then coded according to the used questionnaires guidelines and means, and standard deviations were calculated in Excel.

3 Results

3.1 Samples

Besides continuous involvement of stakeholders, systematic assessments of baseline and prototype evaluation comprised datasets of **60** participants across all conducted activities. Participants were machine operators with reported experience in machine operation from Germany (28), Italy (14), Austria (9), Switzerland (6), Spain (1), Belgium (1) and Hungary (1). The large share of male participants (55, 1 female, and 4 did not specify) reflect the composition of the workforce in this profession, where still is a substantial lack of female and diverse persons. Regarding their affinity for technology interaction, participants reached moderate to fairly high scores with means between 3,83 and 4,92 on the ATI scale (1 – 6 as highest score [13]). Assessment of privacy concerns showed that participants in general have rather high level of privacy concerns (IUIPC = 46.58; SD = 5.52, where the possible values can be from 8 to 56).

41 datasets contributed to the identification of baselines, and 19 datasets contributed to the evaluation of XR demonstrators (6 in use case 1 – snow grooming, 3 in use case 2 – logistics, and 10 in use case 3 – construction). Table 7 summarizes further sample characteristics:

	Baseline evaluation			Prototype evaluation		
	UC1	UC2	UC3	UC1	UC2	UC3
No. of participants	15		14	6	3	10
Age (M, Years)	33,3		30,0	38,7	30,7	30,4
Gender (M/F/D/N.N,)	23/1/0/0		15/0/0/2	6/0/0/0	3/0/0/0	10/0/0/0
Experience (M, Years)	9,6		8,7	16,2	7,0	6,9
ATI (M, SD)	M=4,92 SD=0,54		M=4,46 SD=0,64	M=3,83 SD=0,26	M=4,33 SD=0,88	M=4,15 SD=0,96
PC (M, SD)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	M=49,50, SD=6,16	M=46,00, SD=4,36	M=45,00, SD=5,21

Table 7: Sample description by means of assessed demographic data and individual attitudes

3.2 Use Case 1 – Snow Grooming

Research activities 1, 2 and 5 contributed to the experiment-based evaluation of our XR system in use case 1 – snow grooming. The results are listed in Table 8 below.

Eval. criteria	Evaluation			Baseline			Scale
Task completion	T1	T2	T3	T1	T2	T3	
Work Performance	M=2,58 SD=0,80	M=2,33 SD=0,60	M=1,92 SD=0,20	M=1,67 SD=1,21	M=2,00 SD=1,67	M=2,08 SD=1,74	1 (very good) – 5 (poor)
Crashes/Obstacle rec.	0/18			8/16			Collisions/near miss
Situation Awareness (SART)	M=5,3 SD=1,0	M=6,0 SD=1,0	M=5,1 SD=1,3	M=5,4 SD=9	M=4,6 SD=1,1	M=4, SD=1,3	1 (low) – 7 (high)
Perceived qualities							
Eval. criteria	Evaluation		Baseline		Scale		
Intuitiveness (QUESI)	M=3,8 SD=0,49		M=3,51 SD=0,43				1 (fully disagree) – 5 (fully agree)
Usability (PEOU)	M= 5,56 SD=0,68		–				1 (unlikely) – 7 (likely)
Usability (PU)	M=5,69 SD=1,0		–				1 (unlikely) – 7 (likely)
Predictability	M=4,83 SD=0,41		–				1 (not predictable at all) – 5 (completely predictable)
Comprehensibility	M=4,5 SD=0,55		–				1 (not comprehensible at all) – 5 (Completely comprehensible)
Psy. need for autonomy	3,4		3,6				1 (not at all) – 5 (very much)
Psy. need for competence	3,8		3,6				1 (not at all) – 5 (very much)
Psy. need for self-actualization meaning	3,1		3,5				1 (not at all) – 5 (very much)
Meaningful work	4,4		4,3				0 (do not ag. at all) – 5 (ag. completely)

Meaningless work	0,9	1,4	0 (do not ag. at all) – 5 (ag. completely)
Work as a source of meaning	4,2	4,2	0 (do not ag. at all) – 5 (ag. completely)
Sense of presence (IPQ)	M=3,9 SD=0,9	–	1 – 7 (diverse labels)
Sense of responsibility	3,7	3,6	1 (do not ag. at all) – 5 (ag. completely)

Table 8: Results of conducted use case-specific measures for use case 1. Except for work performance which measured in school grades, higher ratings are better for all other measures.

Work performance measures (safety and efficiency) showed slightly degraded ratings due to limitations in the simulation-based setup. However, the number of collisions was lower in the XR setup compared to the baseline. Except for task 1, situation awareness ratings increased in the XR setup. Intuitiveness remained largely unchanged, with a slight improvement from the baseline to the evaluation. Usability ratings (Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use) resulted good ratings. No baseline was available for these measures in use case 1 due to a malfunction in the questionnaire at this time. Also perceived predictability and comprehensibility of the XR system showed positive ratings. For psychological needs and meaningful work, only the sub-scales are shown that were considered most relevant in this context. Additional needs and facets of meaningful work were collected in the studies but are not reported here. The same applies to use case 3 discussed below. The comparison between baseline and evaluation results for psychological needs and facets of meaningful work shows variations in different directions. However, these results have limited interpretive value, as no concepts aimed at improving these qualities were implemented. Sense of responsibility remained at a similar level, improving slightly from baseline to evaluation.

3.3 Use Case 2 – Logistics

Research activities 6, 7 and 8 contributed to the experiment-based evaluation of our XR system in use case 2. The results are listed in Table 9 below.

Eval. criteria	Evaluation			Baseline			Scale
Task completion	T1	T2	T3	T1	T2	T3	
Work Performance	M=1,83 SD=0,29	M=1,83 SD=0,29	M=2,17 SD=0,29	–	–	–	1 (very good) – 5 (poor)
Improvement Rating (Work Performance)	M=4,67 SD=0,58	M=4,00 SD=1,00	M=4,67 SD=0,58	–	–	–	1 (Significantly worse) - 5 (Significantly better)
Crashes/Obstacle rec.	0			8			Collisions
Situation Awareness (SART)	M=4,1 SD=0,6	M=4,3 SD=0,3	M=4,3 SD=0,7	–	–	–	1 (low) – 7 (high)
Improvement Rating (Situation Awareness)	M=4,33 SD=1,15	M=4,67 SD=0,58	M=4,0 SD=0,0	–	–	–	1 (Significantly worse) - 5 (Significantly better)
Perceived qualities							
Eval. criteria	Evaluation		Baseline		Scale		
Intuitiveness (QUESI)	M=5,0 SD=0,0		–		1 (fully disagree) – 5 (fully agree)		

Usability (PEOU)	M=6,61 SD=0,38	–	1 (unlikely) – 7 (likely)
Improvement Rating (PEOU)	M=5,33 SD=0,58		1 (Significantly worse) - 5 (Significantly better)
Usability (PU)	M=6,83 SD=0,29	–	1 (unlikely) – 7 (likely)
Improvement Rating (PU)	M=4,67 SD=0,58		1 (Significantly worse) - 5 (Significantly better)
Predictability	M=5,0 SD=0,0	–	1 (Not predictable at all) – 5 (Completely predictable)
Comprehensibility	M=4,67 SD=0,58	–	1 (Not comprehensible at all) – 5 (Completely comprehensible)
Psy. need for autonomy	–	–	1 (not at all) – 5 (very much)
Psy. need for competence	–	–	1 (not at all) – 5 (very much)
Psy. need for self-actualization meaning	–	–	1 (not at all) – 5 (very much)
Meaningful work	–	–	0 (do not ag. at all) – 5 (ag. completely)
Meaningless work	–	–	0 (do not ag. at all) – 5 (ag. completely)
Work as a source of meaning	–	–	0 (do not ag. at all) – 5 (ag. completely)
Sense of presence (IPQ)	M=4,2 SD=0,2	–	1 – 7 (diverse labels)
Sense of responsibility	–	–	1 (do not ag. at all) – 5 (ag. completely)

Table 9: Results of conducted use case-specific measures for use case 2. Except for work performance which measured in school grades, higher ratings are better for all other measures.

Work performance measures (safety and efficiency) showed good ratings. No baseline for these measures assessment was conducted due to unavailability of participants. However, the number of collisions in the demonstrator evaluation was lower in the XR setup compared to the baseline. Except for task 1, situation awareness ratings increased in the XR setup. Intuitiveness and usability ratings (Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use) resulted good ratings. No baseline was available for these measures in use case 2 due to unavailability of participants. Comparative ratings for intuitiveness, perceived usefulness and perceived also showed a tendency that these XR are believed to improve the work experience regarding these factors. Also perceived predictability and comprehensibility of the XR system showed positive ratings. No data for psychological needs, meaningful work and sense of responsibility measures could be assessed in use case 2 due to time constraints in the experiments.

3.4 Use Case 3 – Construction

Research activities 3, 4, 9 and 10 contributed to the experiment-based evaluation of our XR system in use case 2. The results are listed in Table 10 below.

Eval. criteria	Evaluation		Baseline		Scale
	T1	T2	T1	T2	
Task completion measures					
Work Performance	M=2,15 SD=0,47	M=2,55 SD=0,60	–	–	1 (very good) – 5 (poor)
Improvement Rating (Work Performance)	M=3,5 SD=0,71	M=3,7 SD=0,95	–	–	1 (Significantly worse) - 5 (Significantly better)
Crashes/Obstacle rec.	0		8		Persons noticed/unnoticed
Situation Awareness (SART)	M=7,1 SD=1,1	M=6,1 SD=1,3	M=6,0 SD=1,1	M=4,1 SD=0,8	1 (low) – 7 (high)
Perceived qualities					
Intuitiveness (QUESI)	M=3,9 SD=0,51		M=3,3 SD=0,84		1 (fully disagree) – 5 (fully agree)
Usability (PEOU)	M=5,92 SD=0,96		–		1 (unlikely) – 7 (likely)
Improvement Rating (PEOU)	M=3,8 SD=1,23		–		1 (Significantly worse) - 5 (Significantly better)
Usability (PU)	M=5,5 SD=1,27		–		1 (unlikely) – 7 (likely)
Improvement Rating (PU)	M=3,9 SD=1,29		–		1 (Significantly worse) - 5 (Significantly better)
Predictability	M=4,1 SD=74		–		1 (Not predictable at all) – 5 (Completely predictable)
Comprehensibility	M=4,3 SD=67		–		1 (Not comprehensible at all) – 5 (Completely comprehensible)
Psy. need for autonomy	4,0		3,5		1 (not at all) – 5 (very much)
Psy. need for competence	3,9		3,8		1 (not at all) – 5 (very much)
Psy. need for self-actualization meaning	2,5		2,6		1 (not at all) – 5 (very much)
Meaningful work	4,4		4,5		0 (do not ag. at all) – 5 (ag. completely)
Meaningless work	0,4		0,4		0 (do not ag. at all) – 5 (ag. completely)
Work as a source of meaning	3,9		3,7		0 (do not ag. at all) – 5 (ag. completely)
Sense of presence (IPQ)	M=3,5 SD=1,1		–		1 – 7 (diverse labels)
Sense of responsibility	4,2		4,2		1 (do not ag. at all) – 5 (ag. completely)

Table 10: Results of conducted use case-specific measures for use case 3. Except for work performance which measured in school grades, higher ratings are better for all other measures.

For use case 3, two tasks were considered: Digging a trench and depositing the excavated material next to the trench (task 1) and avoiding collisions (task 2). The former task 3, which is planning and setting up digital

terrain models/infield design plans, was not considered as it was not included in the simulation. Work performance measures (safety and efficiency) showed good ratings. No baseline for these measures assessment was conducted due to unavailability of participants. However, again assessing number of collisions resulted in a result in the XR setup compared to the baseline. Situation awareness ratings increased for both tasks when using the XR setup. Intuitiveness ratings show a slight improvement from the baseline to the evaluation. Usability ratings (Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use) resulted good ratings. Comparative ratings for intuitiveness, perceived usefulness and perceived also showed a tendency that these XR are believed to improve the work experience regarding these factors. Also perceived predictability and comprehensibility of the XR system showed positive ratings. For psychological needs and meaningful work, only the sub-scales are shown that were considered most relevant in this context. Additional needs and facets of meaningful work were collected in the studies but are not reported here. The same applies to use case 3 discussed below. The comparison between baseline and evaluation results for psychological needs and facets of meaningful work shows variations in different directions. However, these results have limited interpretive value, as no concepts aimed at improving these qualities were implemented. Sense of responsibility remained at a similar level, improving slightly from baseline to evaluation. As in use case 1, the results for psychological needs and facets of meaningful work show different tendencies. As mentioned above, these results only have limited interpretive value.

3.5 General XR qualities

Research activities 5, 6, 9 and 10 contributed to the experiment-based evaluation of our XR system regarding privacy-related measures. The results comprising three subscales of the UEQ+ questionnaire (Trust, and Trustworthiness of Content (TOC)) are listed in Table 11 below.

Eval. criteria	Measure	Scale
Privacy concerns		
User Experience (UEQ+, Trust)	M=22.95 SD=3.26	Max. Score is 28, from 4 bipolar scales, measured from 1(left side of the scale) to 7(right side of the scale with following pairs: insecure / secure; untrustworthy / trustworthy; unreliable / reliable; non-transparent / transparent)
User Experience (UEQ+, ToC)	M=23.81 SD=3.44	Max. Score is 28, from 4 bipolar scales, measured from 1(left side of the scale) to 7(right side of the scale with following pairs: useless / useful; implausible / plausible; untrustworthy / trustworthy; inaccurate / accurate)
Privacy Concerns (MUIPC)	M=26.86, SD=11.14	Max. Score is 63; privacy concerns are measured by 7-point Likert scales (from 1 – not concerned at all to 7 – very much concerned)

Table 11: Results of conducted general privacy related measures

Results are further discussed in deliverable D3.8. “Prototypes for privacy-related questions (final version)”.

3.6 Sense of Presence

Sense of presence (IPQ) was only considered in the evaluation, since the questionnaire relates to the experience of being present in a computer-generated environment. To interpret the results, the IPQ score is compared to a large number of previously published scores [26]. As shown in Figure 2, the IPQ score is low for all use cases. However, the virtual simulations used in the demonstrators were not meant to totally immerse participants but to embed them in realistic task scenarios.

Figure 2: IPQ classification based on previously published scores

4 Discussion

Fulfilment of KPIs regarding the reported experimental measurements for the evaluated XR systems:

Number	Use Cases	Justification of fulfilment for each use case
Task performance-based criteria		
KPI 1.1a	UC1, UC2, UC3	Improvement of safety
		<p>The following dangerous situations (see D3.6) have been mitigated with validated concepts and technologies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Use case 1: Loss of visibility due to fog or storm, accidents involving skiers, accidents involving obstacles – Use case 2: Vehicle tipping over, accidents involving bystanders – Use case 3: Collisions with other vehicles, contact with (water, gas, power) lines in the ground, collisions with objects or persons <p>KPI 1.1a aimed at mitigating three dangerous situations. In total, we succeeded in mitigating a total of eight previously identified dangerous situations.</p>
KPI 1.1b	UC2	Improved perceived presence, awareness and responsibility
		<p>To surpass the perceived presence inside a real machine with a virtual simulation is impossible, which is why the IPQ results should only be seen as an indicator that the demonstrators are unfortunately not yet being perceived as very realistic. This is partly due to hardware, partly software limitations that were difficult to control within the project.</p> <p>Situation awareness, measured by the combined SA (U + S – D) value, has improved in four out of five tasks across use cases 1 and 3, where the SART has been applied. The only task where this was not the case was routine slope preparation in use case 1, which is likely the result of lacking immersion (e.g., the possibility to feel machine movement and observe a real environment in the simulation).</p> <p>It is not clear whether the self-designed scale to measure the sense of responsibility measured the intended effect, but results imply a minor improvement or at least a constancy of values.</p> <p>Due to the limited sample sizes, qualitative statements were collected to back up the identified tendencies described here.</p>

KPI 1.2	UC1, UC2, UC3	Reassurance of intuitiveness and usability
		The prototype-based Evaluation of XR technologies showed good results for usability and intuitiveness across all use cases and prototypes, indicating that the developed systems fit the operators' requirements and expectations.
KPI 2.1	UC1, UC2, UC3	Utility regarding performance evaluated through situational awareness and work performance
		The direct comparison in use case 1 showed a slight deterioration in work performance where assessed qualitative data suggest that this is mainly due to limitations of the simulation used in the demonstration. Comparative measures in use cases 2 and 3 show that participants believe that the demonstrated XR technologies can improve their work quality. Regarding Situational Awareness , except for task 1-based assessment, all other ratings showed an increase in situational awareness. Also, comparative measures in use cases 2 and 3 show that the participants think, that the demonstrated XR technologies can also improve their situational awareness.
KPI 4.2	UC1, UC2, UC3	Improvement of quality of work
		Unfortunately, none of the concepts explicitly developed to address positive UX and improve the quality of work were implemented in the final demonstrators. Thus, any differences in psychological need fulfilment or meaning of work from baselines to prototype evaluations are likely to be incidental. However, UX concept validations reported in D3.7 indicate that an improvement of the quality of work with these concepts is generally possible.
General XR qualities		
KPI 2.2	General	Improved usability
		Perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use ratings reached good scores across all use cases. Comparative measures taken in use case 2 and 3 evaluations also show that participants are convinced, that the demonstrated XR technologies will improve these factors compared to conventional machine operation.
KPI 2.3	General	Better predictability
		Predictability scales showed high ratings across all use cases, indicating that the behaviour of the demonstrated XR technologies were foreseeable. No comparative measures were assessed.
KPI 2.4	General	Improved comprehensibility
		Comprehensibility scales showed high ratings across all use cases, indicating that the behaviour of the demonstrated XR technologies were foreseeable. No comparative measures were assessed.
KPI 4.1	General	Privacy and ethics principles related UX and privacy perceptions
		Results showed that the demonstrated XR technologies did not raised critical privacy perceptions but also fall short in raising awareness which is discuss is further discussed in Deliverable 6.7.

Table 122: List of conducted measures and their association to the XR technology-related KPIs

5 Conclusions

The conducted evaluation activities that involved a set of high-fidelity functional demonstrators of use case specific XR technologies provided quantitative insights regarding defined task-performance and user-experience KPIs. Overall, the results indicate improvements in safety, quality of work, and usability across the investigated use cases, particularly in critical and safety-relevant situations covered by the implemented work tasks in the experiments. Our results also showed positive effects on situational awareness, predictability, and comprehensibility, and high ratings for perceived usefulness and ease of use. While some aspects such as explicit quality-of-work improvements were not always directly measurable, the findings suggest that the proposed concepts support operators effectively without introducing major usability, privacy, or ethical concerns.

6 Appendix

APX1: All components of the modular questionnaire, used for baseline and demonstrator evaluations, in English language

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ABBREVIATIONS / ACRONYMS

[ATI]	Affinity for Technology Interaction
[HMI]	Human-Machine Interface
[IPQ]	Igroup Presence Questionnaire
[UIIPC]	Internet Users' Information Privacy Concerns Questionnaire
[KPI]	Key Performance Indicator
[LED]	Light-emitting Diode, or in general a light source based on this technology
[LiDAR]	Light Detection and Ranging
[ME-Work]	Meaning in Work Inventory Questionnaire
[meCUE]	Fragebogen zur modularen Erfassung nutzerzentrierter Bewertungen im Erleben interaktiver technischer Produkte
[MUIPC]	Mobile users' concerns for information privacy Questionnaire
[QUESI]	Questionnaire for Measuring the Subjective Consequences of Intuitive Use
[QoW]	Quality of Work
[SA]	Situational Awareness
[SART]	Situational Awareness Rating Technique
[SoR]	Sense of Responsibility
[SUS]	System Usability Scale
[TAM]	Technology Acceptance Model
[UEQ]	User Experience Questionnaire
[UC]	Use Case
[UX]	User Experience
[UUX]	Usability and User Experience
[XR]	Extended Reality

Moderator

ST10

Please choose the **preset** associated to your experiment.

If no preset was created, select "Other".

ST14

[Please choose] ▼

Welcome to the THEIA-XR Questionnaire Toolbox

ST01

We implemented adequate standardized questionnaires and open questions to evaluate our XR technologies in regard of our projects KPIs.

Please indicate your experiment scope with the questions on this and the following page.

Associated instructions and questions for the experiment participants will be selected accordingly.

The general procedure is the following:

1. **Introduction** (*same for all use cases*)
2. **Participant consent form** (*same for all use cases*)
3. **Demographic data** (*same for all use cases*)
4. **Task briefing(s)** (*according to the selected use case and task number*)
5. **After task questionnaire(s)** (*after each task*)
6. **After experiment questionnaire** (*after all selected tasks*)
7. **Personal data** (*according to the requirements stated by the Project officer*)
8. **Completion message**

Preset [UC1 Baseline with Simulation] includes the following assets:

ST15

Simulator baseline evaluation for use case 1: Snow Grooming

Tasks:

- Task 1: Basic test of functionality
- Task 2: Collision avoidance
- Task 3: Bad vision navigation

All coupled with a work quality and situation awareness assessment (SART) (to be filled out by the moderator).

Pre-Experiment questionnaire contains:

- ATI (Affinity for Technology Interaction)
- PC (Privacy concerns)

After-experiment questionnaire contains:

- QUESI (intuitiveness)
- SHELDON (psychological need fulfillment)
- MEwork (meaningfulness of work)
- iGroup Presence Questionnaire (presence in a virtual environment)
- Responsibility statements (self-designed)

ST21

Preset [UC1 Baseline with Vehicle] includes the following assets:

Simulator prototype evaluation for use case 1: Snow Grooming

Task 1: Basic test of functionality

Task 2: Collision avoidance

Task 3: Bad vision navigation

All coupled with a work quality assessment (to be filled out by the moderator) and Situational Awareness Rating Technique (SART).

Tasks:

- No specific tasks

Pre-Experiment questionnaire contains:

- ATI (Affinity for Technology Interaction)
- PC (Privacy concerns)

After-experiment questionnaire contains:

- QUESI (intuitiveness)
- SHELDON (psychological need fulfillment)

- MEwork (meaningfulness of work)

- Responsibility statements (self-designed)

Preset [UC1 Prototype Evaluation with Simulation] includes the following assets:

ST22

Simulator prototype evaluation for use case 1: Snow Grooming

Tasks:

- Task 1: Basic test of functionality
- Task 2: Collision avoidance
- Task 3: Bad vision navigation

All coupled with a work quality and situation awareness assessment (SART) (to be filled out by the moderator).

Pre-Experiment questionnaire contains:

- ATI (Affinity for Technology Interaction)
- PC (Privacy concerns)

After-experiment questionnaire contains:

- QUESI (intuitiveness)
- PU/PEOU (perceived usefulness/perceived ease of use)
- UEQ+ (usability and user experience)
- MUIPC (privacy concerns)
- SHELDON (Psychological need fulfillment)
- MEwork (meaningfulness of work)
- iGroup Presence Questionnaire (presence in a virtual environment)
- Responsibility statements (self-designed)
- Qualitative Questions

ST23

Preset [UC1 Prototype Evaluation with Vehicle] includes the following assets:

Simulator prototype evaluation for use case 1: Snow Grooming

Tasks:

- Task 1: Basic test of functionality
- Task 2: Collision avoidance
- Task 3: Bad vision navigation

All coupled with a work quality and situation awareness assessment (SART) (to be filled out by the moderator).

Pre-Experiment questionnaire contains:

- ATI (Affinity for Technology Interaction)
- PC (Privacy concerns)

After-experiment questionnaire contains:

- QUESI (intuitiveness)
- PU/PEOU (perceived usefulness/perceived ease of use)
- UEQ+ (usability and user experience)
- MUIPC (privacy concerns)
- SHELDON (Psychological need fulfillment)
- MEwork (meaningfulness of work)
- Responsibility statements (self-designed)
- Qualitative Questions

Moderator

ST11

Please select or specify the work tasks that your participants will perform during the experiment.

ST03

For each task a separate after-task questionnaire will be implemented into the data assessment procedure.

- Task 1: Prepare a set area of the slope
- Task 2: Avoid collisions during slope preparation
- Task 3: Navigate back to garage in bad vision
- Other

Please select or specify the work tasks that your participants will perform during the experiment.

ST04

For each task a separate after-task questionnaire covering will be implemented into the data assessment procedure.

- Task 1: XX
- Task 2: XX
- Task 3: XX
- Other

Please select or specify the work tasks that your participants will perform during the experiment.

ST05

For each task a separate after-task questionnaire covering will be implemented into the data assessment procedure.

- Task 1: XX
- Task 2: XX
- Task 3: XX
- Other

Please choose which prototype is used for this study.

ST06

If there are any remarks regarding the experiment use this textbox to document any issues or exceptionalities.

ST16

Moderator

(The following content should be read aloud to participants or explained to them.)

Study Briefing: Evaluation of Extended Reality User Interfaces

Procedure:

- In this study, you will be asked to test a simulation, remote control desk or real vehicle demonstrator.
- The purpose of this study is to evaluate the demonstrator and its capabilities, not your performance.
- In the beginning of the study, you will be given some time to try out and get a feeling for the demonstrator.
- In the main part of the study, the moderators will present you with several tasks.
- After each task, the moderators will ask you some questions about your testing experience.
- After all tasks are completed, there will be more questionnaires that we need you to fill out. This is important for us to validate whether we have achieved our measurable project goals.
- In the end, there will be some open questions for you regarding your thoughts on the demonstrator you have used. This part alone will be recorded for our analysis.
- In total, we expect the study to take about 1,5 hours.

If you want to pause or leave the test due to any reason, you can do so anytime without any detriments.

Hand the device with the questionnaire to the participant.

Participant

ST19

Please note the following privacy policy. If you agree, you're ready to go!

IN01

Dear participant,

For evaluation studies in the EU project THEIA-XR between July 29, 2025, and November 30, 2025, we need to collect data on your perception of the vehicle you currently work with and/or the demonstrators we have developed in the project. By participating in this study, you will help us understand and measure the impact of our developed technologies.

Use of personal data

In order to provide our EU project coordinators and the public with a realistic picture of the groups of people we survey, we need some personal data from you. This data will be anonymised for the EU and the public so that it cannot be traced back to you.

Audio recordings

We may need to record a specific part of this study later on (we will inform you beforehand) to gather your opinion on the newly developed technologies in your own words. For these voice recordings only, we may use MAXQDA to transcribe them. The audio recordings will only be used by the Stuttgart Media University of Applied Sciences and the University of Luxembourg and will not be published or passed on to third parties. Anonymised excerpts of the transcripts may be used for scientific publications or social media posts.

Pictures of the study

If you agree, during the study, photos may be taken for the project's public relations purposes (e.g. reports on user studies in publications or on LinkedIn).

Data storage and processing

All personal data, audio recordings, transcripts and photos will be stored on devices, servers and GDPR-compliant cloud service providers under contract with the Technical University of Dresden, the Stuttgart Media University of Applied Sciences and the University of Luxembourg in accordance with the rules of good scientific practice for a period of ten years, after which they will be deleted.

About MAXQDA transcription

The audio recordings are transcribed for analysis. The transcriptions are created using MAXQDA and do not allow any conclusions to be drawn about your identity. MAXQDA Transcription complies with GDPR standards. Media files are deleted immediately after transcription is complete and are used exclusively for transcription, for no other purpose. The transcription servers are located in the EU, in the Netherlands. The transcripts created are stored on servers in Germany and are automatically deleted 7 days after download.

Your rights and our legal basis

After you have completed and submitted the consent form, you still have the right to declare at any time that you no longer consent to the use of the recording. In this case, please contact any of the following responsible persons:

- Manuel Kulzer (kulzer@hdm-stuttgart.de)
- Tanja Brodbeck (brodbeck@hdm-stuttgart.de)
- Sarah Bacher (bacher@hdm-stuttgart.de)
- Sebastian Lorenz (sebastian.lorenz3@tu-dresden.de)
- Anastasia Sergeeva (anastasia.sergeeva@uni.lu)
- Sophie Doublet (sophie.doublet@uni.lu)

Please note that you cannot withdraw your submitted data at a later date, as there is no connection to your name.

I hereby declare,

- that I voluntarily agree to participate in the study.
- that I have been informed in writing about the contents and purposed of the above-mentioned study and the use of my data and that I give my consent to this.
- that I am aware that I can cancel the survey at any time without giving reasons and that I will not suffer any detriments as a result.

No, I do not agree and do not want to participate in this study.

Yes, I agree.

No consent

IN03

Unfortunately, you cannot participate without agreeing to the privacy policy. Thank you for your interest anyway!

Participant

ST19

Part 1: General questions

DE01

In this section, we will ask you some questions about your experience as a vehicle operator.

Please enter a pseudonym for this run.

ST40

The pseudonym consists of the first two letters of the mother's first name, the first two letters of the place of birth, and the month of birth as a two-digit number [example: HELE03].

Participant

ST19

Information about you

SD23

Please enter the following data. We require this information to demonstrate to our EU project sponsors that we are testing our technology demonstrators with real machine operators.

How old are you?

SD19

years old

Which gender do you identify with?

SD01

- female
- male
- diverse
- not specified

What is your Nationality?

SD22

Country:

What is your current occupation?

SD21

How many years of experience do you have in operating snow groomers? An approximate estimate is sufficient.

SD20

years

How many years of experience do you have in operating reach stackers? An approximate estimate is sufficient.

SD24

years

How many years of experience do you have in operating excavators? An approximate estimate is sufficient.

SD25

years

How many years of experience do you have operating mobile machinery? An approximate estimate is sufficient..

SD27

years

DE07

Please rate how well you know how to operate such machines.

Beginner

Expert

Participant

ST19

In the following questionnaire, we will ask you about your interaction with technical systems.

AT02

The term "technical systems" refers to apps and other software applications, as well as entire digital devices (e.g., mobile phone, computer, TV, car navigation).

Please indicate the degree to which you agree/disagree with the following statements.

AT03

	completely disagree	largely disagree	slightly disagree	slightly agree	largely agree	completely agree
I like to occupy myself in greater detail with technical systems.	<input type="radio"/>					
I like testing the functions of new technical systems.	<input type="radio"/>					
It is enough for me that a technical system works; I don't care how or why.	<input type="radio"/>					
It is enough for me to know the basic functions of a technical system.	<input type="radio"/>					

Participant

ST19

Please rate your agreement to the following statements.

PC01

	strongly disagree						strongly agree	
	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	
Consumer online privacy is really a matter of consumers' right to exercise control and autonomy over decisions about how their information is collected, used, and shared.	<input type="radio"/>							
Consumer control of personal information lies at the heart of consumer privacy.	<input type="radio"/>							
Companies seeking information online should disclose the way the data are collected, processed, and used.	<input type="radio"/>							
A good consumer online privacy policy should have a clear and conspicuous disclosure.	<input type="radio"/>							
It usually bothers me when online companies ask me for personal information.	<input type="radio"/>							
When online companies ask me for personal information, I sometimes think twice before providing it.	<input type="radio"/>							
It bothers me to give personal information to so many online companies.	<input type="radio"/>							
I'm concerned that online companies are collecting too much personal information about me.	<input type="radio"/>							

You can now hand in the device with the questionnaire to the study moderator.

ST18

Moderator

ST17

Part 2: Testing the simulation

TI08

You will now be briefed about the functionality of our simulator. After a short familiarization phase you will be given a set of tasks to perform. After each task a short set of questions will be asked. After the completion of all tasks we would love you document your feedback with some additional questions.

Please click "Next" when you feel ready to perform some work tasks with the simulator.

Part 2: Questions on your perception of typical tasks

TI25

In the following, we will ask you about your perception of some typical tasks and situations when working with the vehicle.

Please click on "Next" when you are ready.

Part 2: Testing the prototype

TI26

You will now be briefed about the functionality of our prototype. After a short familiarization phase you will be given a set of tasks to perform. After each task a short set of questions will be asked. After the completion off all tasks we would love you document your feedback with some additional questions.

Please click "Next" when you feel ready to perform some work tasks with the prototype.

Moderator

ST17

[Moderator-Navigation] Select if you want to skip this Task

ST24

- Go to Task 2
- Go to Task 3
- Go to Post-task Questionnaires

Task Briefing

TI24

First task: Basic functionality test

TI09

Your first task will be to try out the basic functionality for grooming a part of a slope.

You will be given further instructions by the test moderators.

Your first task is to load the container labeled T-001T* onto the arriving truck.

TI12

You will receive further instructions from the test moderators.

Your first task is to widen the trench for the next pipe segment. The depth of the trench bottom should be 60 cm below the reference mark. Deposit the excavated material to the left of the trench in the marked area.

TI15

You will receive further instructions from the test moderators.

Moderator

ST17

Quality of Work Assessment (for task 1)

QW04

Please rate the work quality together with the participant regarding each of the following criteria based on grades ranging from 5 (very poor) to 1 (very good):

	1	2	3	4	5
Safety (e.g., collision avoidance, environmental awareness, careful tool and machine maneuvering)	<input type="radio"/>				
Efficiency (e.g., use of resources, effective tool use and machine maneuvering)	<input type="radio"/>				

Please rate the quality of the results compared to your work with conventional machines.

QW22

Significantly worse Slightly worse Equally good/bad Slightly better Significantly better

[Optional] Please indicate further observations you made that contribute to the assessment of work quality in this task.

QW07

What do you think was good about this particular cabin/simulator setup?

QW10

A brief statement is enough.

What do you think was not so good about this particular cabin/simulator setup?

QW13

A brief statement is enough.

Did completing the task in this particular cabin/simulator environment feel different than what you are used to from the real vehicle?

QW16

A brief statement is enough.

While completing the task, what exactly did you personally perceive as better or worse than in the real vehicle that you are used to?

QW19

A brief statement is enough.

Moderator

ST17

Please think back to the task you just completed in the simulation.

SA05

Evaluate the following statements in relation to how you perceived the execution of this task. The term 'situation' in the following questions refers to the completion of this task at the controls of the simulator.

Please think back to a specific, typical working day as a snow groomer operator when you had to **prepare a ski slope or snow park**. Try to visualize as many **details of this working day** as possible, e.g. the condition of the snow.

SA06

Then evaluate the following statements in relation to how you perceived the situation while controlling the vehicle.

For the test moderator: Once the task is completed, please ask the participant to stop the machine and inform them that a questionnaire will follow. Read out the following instructions and the questions of the questionnaire.

SA04

Please think back to the task you just completed in the prototype.

Evaluate the following statements in relation to how you perceived the execution of this task. The term 'situation' in the following questions refers to the completion of this task at the controls of the prototype.

Please answer the following questions on a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 means "low" and 7 means "high".

SA01

	1 (low)	2	3	4	5	6	7 (high)
How changeable is the situation? Is the situation highly unstable and likely to change suddenly (high) or is it very stable and straightforward (low)?	<input type="radio"/>						
How complicated is the situation? Is it complex with many interrelated components (high) or is it simple and straightforward (low)?	<input type="radio"/>						
How many variables are changing within the situation? Are there a large number of factors varying (high) or are there very few variables changing (low)?	<input type="radio"/>						
How aroused are you in the situation? Are you alert and ready for activity (high) or do you have a low degree of alertness (low)?	<input type="radio"/>						
How much are you concentrating on the situation? Are you concentrating on many aspects of the situation (high) or focused on only one (low)?	<input type="radio"/>						
How much is your attention divided in the situation? Are you concentrating on many aspects of the situation (high) or focused on only one (low)?	<input type="radio"/>						
How much mental capacity do you have to spare in the situation? Do you have sufficient to attend to many variables (high) or nothing to spare at all (low)?	<input type="radio"/>						
How much information have you gained about the situation? Have you received and understood a great deal of knowledge (high) or very little (low)?	<input type="radio"/>						
How familiar are you with the situation? Do you have a great deal of relevant experience (high) or is it a new situation (low)?	<input type="radio"/>						

SA09

Please rate your assessment of situational awareness in comparison to your work with conventional machines.

Significantly worse

slightly worse

Equally good/bad

Slightly better

Significantly better

Moderator

ST17

[Moderator-Navigation] Select if you want to skip this Task

ST25

- Go to Task 3
- Go to Post-task Questionnaires

Task Briefing

TI24

Task 2: Obstacle avoidance test

TI10

Your second task is to prepare another section of the slope while avoiding collisions.
You will receive further instructions from the test moderators.

Your second task is to store the containers unloaded by the portal crane in area A*.
You will receive further instructions from the test moderators.

TI13

Your second task is to excavate the marked construction pit to a depth of 2 meters. Create a 45° slope and try to work as quickly as possible. Dump the excavated material into the container behind you. If someone is in the way, stop briefly and sound the horn.
You will receive further instructions from the test moderators.

TI16

Moderator

ST17

[Moderator] Quality of Work Assessment (for task 2)

QW05

Please rate the work quality together with the participant regarding each of the following criteria based on grades ranging from 5 (very poor) to 1 (very good):

	1	2	3	4	5
Safety (e.g., collision avoidance, environmental awareness, careful tool and machine maneuvering)	<input type="radio"/>				
Efficiency (e.g., use of resources, effective tool use and machine maneuvering)	<input type="radio"/>				

Please rate the quality of the results compared to your work with conventional machines.

QW23

- Significantly worse Slightly worse Equally good/bad Slightly better Significantly better

[Optional] Please indicate further observations you made that contribute to the assessment of work quality in this task.

QW08

What do you think was good about this particular cabin/simulator setup?

QW11

A brief statement is enough.

Did completing the task in this particular cabin/simulator environment feel different than what you are used to from the real vehicle?

QW17

A brief statement is enough.

What do you think was not so good about this particular cabin/simulator setup?

QW14

A brief statement is enough.

While completing the task, what exactly did you personally perceive as better or worse than in the real vehicle that you are used to?

QW20

A brief statement is enough.

Moderator

ST17

Please think back to the task you just completed in the simulation.

SA05

Evaluate the following statements in relation to how you perceived the execution of this task. The term 'situation' in the following questions refers to the completion of this task at the controls of the simulator.

Please think back to a specific, typical working day as an snow groomer operator when you had to **avoid skiers, animals or other vehicles on the slope that were not supposed to be there**. Try to visualise as many **details of this working day** as possible, e.g., how you noticed the skiers, animals or vehicles approaching and how you reacted to them.

SA07

Then evaluate the following statements in relation to how you perceived the situation while controlling the vehicle.

For the test moderator: Once the task is completed, please ask the participant to stop the machine and inform them that a questionnaire will follow. Read out the following instructions and the questions of the questionnaire.

SA04

Please think back to the task you just completed in the prototype.

Evaluate the following statements in relation to how you perceived the execution of this task. The term 'situation' in the following questions refers to the completion of this task at the controls of the prototype.

Please answer the following questions on a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 means "low" and 7 means "high".

SA02

	1 (low)	2	3	4	5	6	7 (high)
How changeable is the situation? Is the situation highly unstable and likely to change suddenly (high) or is it very stable and straightforward (low)?	<input type="radio"/>						
How complicated is the situation? Is it complex with many interrelated components (high) or is it simple and straightforward (low)?	<input type="radio"/>						
How many variables are changing within the situation? Are there a large number of factors varying (high) or are there very few variables changing (low)?	<input type="radio"/>						
How aroused are you in the situation? Are you alert and ready for activity (high) or do you have a low degree of alertness (low)?	<input type="radio"/>						
How much are you concentrating on the situation? Are you concentrating on many aspects of the situation (high) or focused on only one (low)?	<input type="radio"/>						
How much is your attention divided in the situation? Are you concentrating on many aspects of the situation (high) or focused on only one (low)?	<input type="radio"/>						
How much mental capacity do you have to spare in the situation? Do you have sufficient to attend to many variables (high) or nothing to spare at all (low)?	<input type="radio"/>						
How much information have you gained about the situation? Have you received and understood a great deal of knowledge (high) or very little (low)?	<input type="radio"/>						
How familiar are you with the situation? Do you have a great deal of relevant experience (high) or is it a new situation (low)?	<input type="radio"/>						

SA10

Please rate your assessment of situational awareness in comparison to your work with conventional machines.

Significantly worse

slightly worse

Equally good/bad

Slightly better

Significantly better

Moderator

ST17

[Moderator-Navigation] Select if you want to skip this Task

ST26

Go to Post-task Questionnaires

Task Briefing

TI24

Task 3: Bad vision navigation test

TI11

Your third task is to navigate the slope during bad weather conditions.

You will receive further instructions from the test moderators.

Your third task is to pick up container T-003T from the lorry with identification X and take it to loading point Y.

TI14

You will receive further instructions from the test moderators.

Your third task is to create a subgrade in accordance with the reference markings for the entire area. Work carefully and ensure that the entire area is within the tolerance of ± 3 cm.

TI17

You will receive further instructions from the test moderators.

Moderator

ST17

Quality of Work Assessment (for task 3)

QW06

Please rate the work quality together with the participant regarding each of the following criteria based on grades ranging from 5 (very poor) to 1 (very good):

	1	2	3	4	5
Safety (e.g., collision avoidance, environmental awareness, careful tool and machine maneuvering)	<input type="radio"/>				
Efficiency (e.g., use of resources, effective tool use and machine maneuvering)	<input type="radio"/>				

Please rate the quality of the results compared to your work with conventional machines.

QW24

- Significantly worse Slightly worse Equally good/bad Slightly better Significantly better

[Optional] Please indicate further observations you made that contribute to the assessment of work quality in this task.

QW09

What do you think was good about this particular cabin/simulator setup?

QW12

A brief statement is enough.

What do you think was not so good about this particular cabin/simulator setup?

QW15

A brief statement is enough.

Did completing the task in this particular cabin/simulator environment feel different than what you are used to from the real vehicle?

QW18

A brief statement is enough.

While completing the task, what exactly did you personally perceive as better or worse than in the real vehicle that you are used to?

QW21

A brief statement is enough.

Moderator

ST17

Please think back to the task you just completed in the simulation.

SA05

Evaluate the following statements in relation to how you perceived the execution of this task. The term 'situation' in the following questions refers to the completion of this task at the controls of the simulator.

Please think back to a specific, typical working day as an snow groomer operator when you had to **navigate your snow groomer during a snow storm, dense fog or other situation with bad visibility**. Try to visualize as many **details of this working day** as possible.

SA08

Then evaluate the following statements in relation to how you perceived the situation while controlling the vehicle.

For the test moderator: Once the task is completed, please ask the participant to stop the machine and inform them that a questionnaire will follow. Read out the following instructions and the questions of the questionnaire.

SA04

Please think back to the task you just completed in the prototype.

Evaluate the following statements in relation to how you perceived the execution of this task. The term 'situation' in the following questions refers to the completion of this task at the controls of the prototype.

Please answer the following questions on a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 means "low" and 7 means "high".

SA03

	1 (low)	2	3	4	5	6	7 (high)
How changeable is the situation? Is the situation highly unstable and likely to change suddenly (high) or is it very stable and straightforward (low)?	<input type="radio"/>						
How complicated is the situation? Is it complex with many interrelated components (high) or is it simple and straightforward (low)?	<input type="radio"/>						
How many variables are changing within the situation? Are there a large number of factors varying (high) or are there very few variables changing (low)?	<input type="radio"/>						
How aroused are you in the situation? Are you alert and ready for activity (high) or do you have a low degree of alertness (low)?	<input type="radio"/>						
How much are you concentrating on the situation? Are you concentrating on many aspects of the situation (high) or focused on only one (low)?	<input type="radio"/>						
How much is your attention divided in the situation? Are you concentrating on many aspects of the situation (high) or focused on only one (low)?	<input type="radio"/>						
How much mental capacity do you have to spare in the situation? Do you have sufficient to attend to many variables (high) or nothing to spare at all (low)?	<input type="radio"/>						
How much information have you gained about the situation? Have you received and understood a great deal of knowledge (high) or very little (low)?	<input type="radio"/>						
How familiar are you with the situation? Do you have a great deal of relevant experience (high) or is it a new situation (low)?	<input type="radio"/>						

Please rate your assessment of situational awareness in comparison to your work with conventional machines.

SA11

- Significantly worse
 slightly worse
 Equally good/bad
 Slightly better
 Significantly better

Moderator

ST17

Part 3: Final questions

TI19

When all tasks are completed, please read aloud or explain the following:

"Now that we are done with the individual tasks, we have a few more questionnaires for you to find out how you perceived the whole experience of using the vehicle/simulator. I will return this device to you so you can fill out the questionnaires yourself."

Hand the device with the questionnaire to the participant.

ST20

Participant

ST19

Intuitiveness and ease of use

QU06

The following questionnaire is about your perception of how easy or difficult the snow groomer simulator was to operate.

Please evaluate the following statements based on your personal perception. There are no right or wrong answers, just try to answer spontaneously.

Base your assessment solely on the use of the vehicle (and not, for example, on the difficulty of the tasks you performed with the vehicle). The term 'system' in the following statements refers to the simulator, its controls and the on-board systems (displays, software, etc.) that you used.

Intuitiveness and ease of use

QU10

The following questionnaire is about your perception of how easy or difficult it was to learn how to operate an excavator.

Think back to your early days as an excavator operator, e.g. the first time you dug a construction pit or trench to a specified depth. Then evaluate the following statements based on your memory. There are no right or wrong answers, just try to answer spontaneously.

Base your assessment solely on the use of the vehicle (and not, for example, on the difficulty of the tasks you performed with the vehicle). The term 'system' in the following statements refers to the vehicle itself, its controls and the on-board systems (displays, software, etc.) that you used.

Intuitiveness and ease of use

QU04

The following questionnaire focuses on your perception of how easy or difficult it was to learn how to operate a snow groomer.

Please think back to your first experiences as a snow groomer operator, e.g. the first time you groomed a ski slope. Then evaluate the following statements based on your memory. There are no right or wrong answers, just try to answer spontaneously.

Base your assessment solely on the use of the vehicle (and not, for example, on the difficulty of the tasks you performed with it). The term 'system' in the following statements refers to the vehicle itself, its controls and the on-board systems (displays, software, etc.) that you used.

Intuitiveness and ease of use

QU05

The following questionnaire is about your perception of how easy or difficult the snow groomer prototype was to operate.

Please evaluate the following statements based on your personal perception. There are no right or wrong answers, just try to answer spontaneously.

Base your assessment solely on the use of the vehicle (and not, for example, on the difficulty of the tasks you performed with the vehicle). The term 'system' in the following statements refers to the simulator, its controls and the on-board systems (displays, software, etc.) that you used.

Intuitiveness and ease of use

QU11

The following questionnaire is about your perception of how easy or difficult the snow groomer simulator was to operate.

Please evaluate the following statements based on your personal perception. There are no right or wrong answers, just try to answer spontaneously.

Base your assessment solely on the use of the vehicle (and not, for example, on the difficulty of the tasks you performed with the vehicle). The term 'system' in the following statements refers to the simulator, its controls and the on-board systems (displays, software, etc.) that you used.

QU01

Please assess the next statements.

	Fully disagree	Mainly disagree	Neutral	Mainly agree	Fully agree
I could use the system without thinking about it.	<input type="radio"/>				
I achieved what I wanted to achive with the system.	<input type="radio"/>				
The way the system worked was immediately clear to me.	<input type="radio"/>				
I could interact with the system in a way that seemed familiar to me.	<input type="radio"/>				
No problems occurred when I used the system.	<input type="radio"/>				
The system was not complicated to use.	<input type="radio"/>				
I was able to achieve my goals in the way I had imagined.	<input type="radio"/>				
The system was easy to use from the start.	<input type="radio"/>				
It was always clear to me what I had to do to use the system.	<input type="radio"/>				
The process of using the system went smoothly.	<input type="radio"/>				
I barely had to concentrate on using the system.	<input type="radio"/>				
The system helped me to completely achieve my goals.	<input type="radio"/>				
How the system is used was clear to me straight away.	<input type="radio"/>				
I automatically did the right thing to achieve my goals.	<input type="radio"/>				

Please rate the intuitiveness in comparison to the conventional machine operation you are familiar with.

QU09

Significantly worse

Slightly worse

Equally good/bad

Slightly better

Significantly better

Participant

ST19

Please rate your agreement with the following statements on usefulness.

PU01

	unlikely						likely
Using the system in my job would enable me to accomplish tasks more quickly.	<input type="radio"/>						
Using the system would improve my job performance.	<input type="radio"/>						
Using the system in my job would increase my productivity.	<input type="radio"/>						
Using the system would enhance my effectiveness on the job.	<input type="radio"/>						
Using the system would make it easier to do my job.	<input type="radio"/>						
I would find the system useful in my job.	<input type="radio"/>						

Please rate the usefulness in comparison to the conventional machine operation you are familiar with.

PU08

<input type="radio"/>				
Significantly worse	Slightly worse	Equally good/bad	Slightly better	Significantly better

Please rate your agreement with the statements below regarding user-friendliness.

PU02

	unlikely						likely
Learning to operate the system would be easy for me	<input type="radio"/>						
I would find it easy to get the system to do what I want it to do.	<input type="radio"/>						
My interaction with the system would be clear and understandable.	<input type="radio"/>						
I would find the system to be flexible to interact with.	<input type="radio"/>						
It would be easy for me to become skillful at using the system.	<input type="radio"/>						
I would find the system easy to use.	<input type="radio"/>						

Please rate the user-friendliness in comparison to the conventional machine operation you are familiar with.

PU07

<input type="radio"/>				
Significantly worse	Slightly worse	Equally good/bad	Slightly better	Significantly better

Participant

ST19

Please provide your assessment.

UQ22

The following questionnaire consists of pairs of opposites of properties that the XR-system may have. By ticking one of these circles, you can express your tendency to one or the other term. Decide as spontaneously as possible. There is no "right" or "wrong" answer. Only your personal opinion counts!

In my opinion, the product is generally...

UQ01

annoying	<input type="radio"/>	enjoyable						
bad	<input type="radio"/>	good						
unpleasant	<input type="radio"/>	pleasant						
unfriendly	<input type="radio"/>	friendly						

Regarding the use of my personal information and data, the product is...

UQ08

insecure	<input type="radio"/>	secure						
untrustworthy	<input type="radio"/>	trustworthy						
unreliable	<input type="radio"/>	reliable						
non-transparent	<input type="radio"/>	transparent						

In my opinion, the information and data provided by the product are...

UQ16

useless	<input type="radio"/>	useful						
implausible	<input type="radio"/>	plausible						
untrustworthy	<input type="radio"/>	trustworthy						
inaccurate	<input type="radio"/>	accurate						

Please rate the predictability of the behavior of the XR feedback.

UQ23

<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Not predictable at all	Hardly predictable	Inconclusive	Rather predictable	Completely predictable

UQ24

Participant

ST19

The following questionnaire concerns your perception of the use of the simulator.

SH06

There are no right or wrong answers, just try to answer spontaneously.

The term 'system' in the following statements refers to the snow groomer simulator, its controls and the on-board systems (displays, software, etc.) that you have used.

The following questionnaire concerns your perception of the use of snow groomers in the past.

SH04

There are no right or wrong answers, just try to answer spontaneously.

The term 'system' in the following statements refers to the snow groomer, its controls and the on-board systems (displays, software, etc.) that you typically use or have used.

The following questionnaire concerns your perception of the use of excavators in the past.

SH07

There are no right or wrong answers, just try to answer spontaneously.

The term 'system' in the following statements refers to the excavator, its controls and the on-board systems (displays, software, etc.) that you typically use or have used.

The following questionnaire concerns your perception of the use of the snow groomer.

SH05

There are no right or wrong answers, just try to answer spontaneously.

The term 'system' in the following statements refers to the snow groomer, its controls and the on-board systems (displays, software, etc.) that you have used.

The following questionnaire concerns your perception of the use of the simulator.

SH08

There are no right or wrong answers, just try to answer spontaneously.

The term 'system' in the following statements refers to the snow groomer simulator, its controls and the on-board systems (displays, software, etc.) that you have used.

SH01

During the usage of the system I felt...

not at all

very much

That my choices were based on my true interests and values.	<input type="radio"/>				
Free to do things my own way.	<input type="radio"/>				
That my choices expressed my "true self."	<input type="radio"/>				
That I was successfully completing difficult tasks and projects.	<input type="radio"/>				
That I was taking on and mastering hard challenges.	<input type="radio"/>				
Very capable in what I did.	<input type="radio"/>				
A sense of contact with people who care for me, and whom I care for.	<input type="radio"/>				
Close and connected with other people who are important to me.	<input type="radio"/>				
A strong sense of intimacy with the people I spent time with.	<input type="radio"/>				
That I was "becoming who I really am."	<input type="radio"/>				
A sense of deeper purpose in life.	<input type="radio"/>				
A deeper understanding of myself and my place in the universe.	<input type="radio"/>				
That I was experiencing new sensations and activities.	<input type="radio"/>				
Intense physical pleasure and enjoyment.	<input type="radio"/>				
That I had found new sources and types of stimulation for myself.	<input type="radio"/>				
That my life was structured and predictable.	<input type="radio"/>				
Glad that I have a comfortable set of routines and habits.	<input type="radio"/>				
Safe from threats and uncertainties.	<input type="radio"/>				
That I had many positive qualities.	<input type="radio"/>				
Quite satisfied with who I am.	<input type="radio"/>				
A strong sense of self-respect.	<input type="radio"/>				
That I was a person whose advice others seek out and follow.	<input type="radio"/>				
That I strongly influenced others' beliefs and behavior.	<input type="radio"/>				
That I had strong impact on what other people did.	<input type="radio"/>				

Participant

ST19

The following questionnaire concerns your perception of the snow groomer simulation and the vehicle prototype.
There are no right or wrong answers, just try to answer spontaneously.

PQ16

The following questionnaire concerns your perception of the reach stacker simulation and the vehicle prototype.
There are no right or wrong answers, just try to answer spontaneously.

PQ17

The following questionnaire concerns your perception of the excavator simulation and the vehicle prototype.
There are no right or wrong answers, just try to answer spontaneously.

PQ18

In the computer generated world I had a sense of “being there”.

PQ01

not at all very much

Somehow I felt that the virtual world surrounded me.

PQ02

fully disagree fully agree

I felt like I was just perceiving pictures.

PQ03

fully disagree fully agree

I did not feel present in the virtual space.

PQ04

did not feel felt present

I had a sense of acting in the virtual space, rather than operating something from outside.

PQ05

fully disagree fully agree

I felt present in the virtual space.

PQ06

fully disagree fully agree

How aware were you of the real world surrounding while navigating in the virtual world? (i.e., sounds, room temperature, other people, etc.)?

PQ07

extremely aware not aware at all

I was not aware of my real environment.

PQ08

fully disagree fully agree

PQ09

Participant

ST19

The following questionnaire concerns your perception of safety and control while driving the simulator you have just experienced.
There are no right or wrong answers; just try to answer spontaneously.

RS04

The following questionnaire is about how safe and in control you feel when driving your vehicle.
There are no right or wrong answers; just try to answer spontaneously.

RS02

The following questionnaire concerns your perception of safety and control while driving the vehicle you have just driven.
There are no right or wrong answers; just try to answer spontaneously.

RS03

Please indicate how much you agree with the statements for your work context.

RS01

	Don't agree at all			Agree completely	
I feel obliged to prevent any accidents on the slope from happening.	<input type="radio"/>				
I am confident that I can prevent any accidents on the slope from happening.	<input type="radio"/>				
I would feel personally responsible if it came to a collision between a skier and my vehicle.	<input type="radio"/>				
The technology inside the vehicle enables me to react to possible dangers in time and appropriately.	<input type="radio"/>				
I would feel personally responsible if there was an accident on a part of a slope during the day that I had prepared.	<input type="radio"/>				
The technology inside the vehicle allows me to prepare a slope precisely and efficiently.	<input type="radio"/>				

Please indicate how much you agree with the statements for your work context.

RS05

	Don't agree at all			Agree completely	
I feel obliged to prevent any accidents on the construction site from happening.	<input type="radio"/>				
I am confident that I can prevent any accidents on the construction site from happening.	<input type="radio"/>				
I would feel personally responsible if it came to a collision between a bystander and my vehicle.	<input type="radio"/>				
The technology inside the vehicle enables me to react to possible dangers in time and appropriately.	<input type="radio"/>				
I would feel personally responsible if there was an accident on a part of a construction site that I have worked on.	<input type="radio"/>				
The technology inside the vehicle allows me to work precisely and efficiently.	<input type="radio"/>				

You can now hand in the device with the questionnaire to the study moderator.

ST18

Moderator

ST17

For this part of the questionnaire, a voice recording is needed. Inform the participant about the voice recording being started now. Alternatively, should they not want to be recorded, notes can be taken directly in the questionnaire.

SC17

To summarize your experience, please complete the following questions.
Don't overthink your responses; answer as spontaneously as possible.

Do you believe the XR functions can make your work more efficient?

SC02

(briefly explain)

Do you believe the XR functions can make your work less efficient?

SC10

(briefly explain)

Do you believe the XR functions can make your work more enjoyable?

SC11

(briefly explain)

Do you believe the XR functions can make your work less enjoyable?

SC12

(briefly explain)

Do you believe the XR functions will be easy to use it?

SC13

(briefly explain)

Do you believe the XR functions will be hard to use it?

SC14

(briefly explain)

Do you believe the XR functions will make your work safer?

SC15

(briefly explain)

Do you think the XR functions will make your work more dangerous?

SC16

(briefly explain)

Thank you for completing this questionnaire!

We would like to thank you very much for helping us.

Your answers were submitted, you may close the browser window or tab now.